

1 **Lmod1 and Lmod2 function in lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Lmod1
8 and Lmod2 as lineage commitment factors or lineage commitment cooperating factors in embryonic stem
9 cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Halim, D., Wilson, M.P., Oliver, D., Brosens, E., Verheij, J.B., Han, Y., Nanda, V., Lyu, Q., Doukas,
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